

×*Echinosteles*, a New Nothogenus in Cactaceae

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Abstract—The nothogenus ×*Echinosteles* (= *Echinopsis* × *Leucosteles*) and the new combination ×*Echinosteles cabreræ* are proposed.

Echinopsis cabreræ is listed by Edward F. Anderson (*The Cactus Family*: 260. 2001) and David Hunt (*The New Cactus Lexicon*: 93. 2006) as a probable hybrid between *Echinopsis strigosa* and *Echinopsis terscheckii*. Since the latter species is now placed in *Leucosteles*, a new nothogenus and a new combination are needed:

×*Echinosteles* M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.**

= *Echinopsis* Zucc. × *Leucosteles* Backeb.

<https://www.cactusnames.org/echinosteles>

×*Echinosteles cabreræ* (Kiesling) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

≡ *Trichocereus cabreræ* R.Kiesling, pro sp. — *Hickenia* 1(6): 30 (-31) (1976)

≡ *Echinopsis cabreræ* (R.Kiesling) G.D.Rowley, pro sp.

= *Echinopsis strigosa* (Salm-Dyck) H.Friedrich & G.D.Rowley × *Leucosteles terscheckii* (Pfeiff.) Schlumpb.

<https://www.cactusnames.org/echinosteles-cabreræ>

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